

activation parameters are $E_a=67.7$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta H^\ddagger=65.1$ kJ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta S^\ddagger=-56$ JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. The possibility of radical involvement in the reaction was ruled out as the addition of acrylamide in the reaction mixture did not initiate polymerisation. It was also confirmed by low value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$.

The possible oxidising species in acidified CAB solution are RNHCl, RNCl₂, HOCl, Cl₂ and H₂OCl⁺. Bishop and Jennings first approximation calculations on 0.1 M solutions of CAT shows that the concentration of RNHCl is high at pH 0–3. Considering the experimental conditions and observations the most probable mechanistic pathway is given below.

The Scheme leads to the rate law,

$$-d[\text{CAB}]/dt = k'_2 [\text{RNH}_2\text{Cl}^+]^2$$

After omitting the higher terms,

$$-d[\text{CAB}]/dt = \frac{k'_2 K_2^2 [\text{CAB}]_0^2 [\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + 2K_1 [\text{CAB}]_0 + 2K_1 [\text{H}^+]}$$

The rate law accords well with the kinetic orders in oxidant, substrate and acid.

Quinlan-Amis equation^{4, 5} for ion-dipolar molecule reaction is in accordance with the effect of ionic strength on the reaction rate. In the presence of Cl⁻, the reaction is very fast. It may be due to the formation of Cl₂,

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Mechanism of Oxidation of Aromatic Amine by Periodate. Further Supporting Evidence

SATYA PRAKASH SRIVASTAVA,

GURUDAS BHATTACHARJEE* and PRATIBHA MALIK

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee,
Roorkee-247 667

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THE mechanism of oxidation of aromatic amine has been studied using various oxidants¹, but no conclusive mechanism has yet emerged and those available are at variance with each other. The nature of the product vary from oxidant to oxidant, hence to arrive at a reasonable conclusion, sufficient data covering a wide variety of substrates are required.

We have carried out a detailed kinetic study on the oxidation of 2,5-dimethylaniline by periodate ion in 2.5% (v/v) acetic acid–water. The reaction rate decreased with decreased dielectric constant and increased ionic strength of the medium. The reaction was pH-dependent. The main oxidation product was confirmed to be 2,5-dimethyl-*p*-benzoquinone². The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be 2 : 1 (oxidant : substrate). On the basis of kinetic and non-kinetic evidences we proposed³ a bimolecular interaction mechanism with the rate-limiting formation for an activated complex (A) possessing a positively charged nitrogen in direct conjugation with the aromatic ring (structure A, Scheme 1). Subsequently, to confirm the existence of such a species, we have studied periodate oxidation of a number of mono substituted anilines (X–C₆H₄NH₂; X=H, *p*-Cl, *p*-Br, *p*-I, *p*-Me, *p*-OMe and *p*-OEt) under similar conditions with a view to evaluate electronic substituent effect.

The concentration range used for the amine³ and the oxidant were 1.0–1.5 × 10⁻³ and 1.0–1.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ respectively. However, in the case of *p*-methoxy- and *p*-ethoxyanilines much lower concentration of the reactants (amine and oxidant, 3.0 × 10⁻³ and 3.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ respectively) was used. The reaction was followed at the λ_{max} of the principal product (Table 1) on a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 100 spectrophotometer. Guggenheim and Swinbourne methods⁴ were not applicable for calculation of rate constant. Hence initial rate, (dA/dt)_i, calculated by plane mirror method⁵ was taken as the first order rate constant, k₁. A plot of log k₂ (k₂=second order rate constant) versus σ⁺ shows that substituents having lone-pair of electron, such as *p*-Cl, *p*-Br, *p*-I, *p*-OMe, exhibit a reasonably good linear relationship (ρ = -2.3). Such group effectively stabilise the activated complex by direct resonance interaction. In the case of *p*-Me group, only a weak hyperconjugative effect is operating. The slight deviation observed in this case may not

TABLE 1—OXIDATION OF SUBSTITUTED-ANILINES BY PERIODATE ION

Medium: 2.5% (v/v) acetic acid-water, Temp. = 25 ± 0.1°
 [Substrate] = (1.0–1.5) × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³,
 [oxidant] = (1.0–1.5) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³

X	λ _{max} nm	Colour of product	k ₂ × 10 ⁴ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	σ ⁺
H	345	Yellowish brown	4.3	0
p-Cl	425	Brown	3.1	0.114
p-Br	440	Yellowish brown	2.5	0.15
p-I	540	Reddish brown	2.3	0.135
p-Me	470	Dark violet	8.8	-0.31
p-OMe	560	Bluish violet	89	-0.78
p-OEt	480	Violet	94	—

For *p*-methoxy- and *p*-ethoxyanilines the substrate and oxidant concentrations were 3.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ and 3.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ respectively.

be unexpected in the light of discussion by Schreck⁶. The relatively lower rates observed in the case of *p*-halo substituents may be partly attributed to the coherent electron-withdrawing effect. Keeping in mind the structure of the proposed² activated complex, it may be inferred that *meta*-substituted anilines should exhibit lower reactivity due to the fact that *meta*-substituents cannot effectively meet the high electron demand of the transition state because of the absence of direct resonance interaction and this has been found to be so in practice. The existence of a linear relationship between log k₂ and σ⁺ with a negative ρ value of 2.3 support our earlier view on mechanism of oxidation of 2,5-dimethylaniline by periodate². The relatively faster rates of oxidation observed in the case of *p*-methoxy- and *p*-ethoxyanilines point to the ease of stability of the transition states formed in these cases as

Scheme 1

envisaged. The general scheme of mechanism is shown in Schemes 1 and 2. For *para*-substituted anilines it may be inferred that attack by water molecule takes place at the *ortho*-position in structure (C) in Scheme 1 instead of at *para*-position, and subsequent transformations occur in a similar manner resulting finally in the formation of *p*-substituted *o*-benzoquinone.

Scheme 2. For 2,3-dimethylaniline R¹=R²=Me, R³=H; for 2,5-dimethylaniline R¹=R³=Me, R²=H.

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